

Anhang-1 Charakteristische Merkmale der Studien

Title	Autor	Jahr	Methode
Teachers' viewpoints about an educational reform concerning multilingualism in German-speaking Switzerland	Lundberg	2019	Q Method*
Monolingual ideologies confronting multilingual realities. Finnish teachers' beliefs about linguistic diversity	Alisaari et al.	2019	Quantitative
What about Elementary Level Teachers: A Closer Look at the Intersection between Standardization and Multilingualism	Barrenechea	2018	Qualitative
Multilingualism and Multiculturalism in the Swedish-Medium Primary School Classroom in Finland - Some Teacher Views	Björklund	2013	Qualitative
Collective teachers' beliefs about multilingualism in Maltese primary education	Camenzuli et al.	2022	Q Method*
'The inappropriateness of language': discourses of power and control over languages beyond English in primary schools	Cunningham	2019	Qualitative
Does the use of migrant languages in German primary schools transform language orders? Findings from ethnographic classroom investigations	Dlugaj &ürstenau	2019	Qualitative
Teachers' beliefs in multilingual education in the Basque country and in Friesland	Egaña et al.	2015	Qualitative
'If I Wanted To Survive I Had To Use It': The Power of Teacher Beliefs on Classroom Practices	Farrell	2019	Qualitative
"We speak English in here and English only!": Teacher and ELL youth perspectives on restrictive language education	Fredricks & Warriner	2016	Qualitative
Teachers' beliefs about multilingualism in a course on translanguaging	Gorter & Arocena	2020	Quantitative
Teachers' beliefs concerning teaching multilingual learners: a cross-cultural comparison between the US and Germany	Hammer et al.	2018	Quantitative
Influences on Teachers' Use of the Prescribed Language of Instruction: Evidence from Four Language Groups in the Philippines	Harden et al.	2022	Qualitative
Teacher beliefs and approaches to linguistic diversity. Spanish as a second language in the inclusion of immigrant students	Rodríguez-Izquierdo et al.	2020	Qualitative
The impact of teacher professional development on teacher cognition and multilingual teaching practices	Krulatz et al.	2022	Quantitative
Teachers' beliefs about multilingualism: findings from Q method research	Lundberg	2018	Q Method*
Translanguaging and minoritised language revitalisation in multilingual classrooms: Examining teachers' agency	Maseko	2022	Qualitative
Multilingual Students in Greek Schools: Teachers' Views and Teaching Practices	Mitits	2018	Quantitative
Namibian Teachers' Beliefs about Medium of Instruction and Language Education Policy Implementation	Norro	2022	Mixed Method
Towards a practical proposal for multilingualism in education in Kenya	Oduor	2015	Qualitative
The utilisation of translanguaging for learning and teaching in multilingual primary classrooms	Omidire & Ayob	2020	Qualitative
Supportive primary teacher beliefs towards multilingualism through teacher training and professional practice	Pohlmann-Rother et al.	2022	Quantitative

'It is okay if you speak another language, but ... ':language hierarchies in mono- and bilingual school teachers' beliefs	Putjata & Koster	2021	Qualitative
Bilingual education in Mozambique: a case-study on educational policy, teacher beliefs, and implemented practices	Terra	2018	Qualitative
Opening up towards children's languages: enhancing teachers' tolerant practices towards multilingualism	Van Der Wildt et al.	2017	Quantitative
Developing language awareness for teachers of emergent bilingual learners using dialogic inquiry	Wallen & Kelly-Holmes	2017	Qualitative
Multilingual school population: ensuring school belonging by tolerating multilingualism	Van Der Wildt et al.	2017	Quantitative
Legitimizing Multilingual Teacher Identities in the Mainstream Classroom	Higgins & Ponte	2017	Qualitative
Multilingual Classrooms—Danish Teachers' Practices, Beliefs and Attitudes	Knudsen	2021	Quantitative
Preservice and Inservice Teachers' Language Ideologies about Non-Spanish-Speaking Students and Multilingualism in Chilean Classrooms	Toledo et al.	2022	Mixed Method
Teachers' beliefs on multilingualism in the Basque Country: Basque at the core of multilingual education	Gartziarena & Villabona	2022	Mixed Method

* Kombiniert qualitative und quantitative Datenanalysen.